

THE SOCIAL FESTIVALS AND EVENTS FOR DESTINATION BRANDING AND PROMOTION IN ASIAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract

Festivals provide joy and tranquility to many cities, attracting many people. The festival image may be a critical component of the region's brand development process since it may imprint the final tourist product. As a result, festival brands frequently affect how a region's overall brand is perceived. Festivals are gaining popularity to enhance a region's image and attractiveness, provide recreational opportunities, contribute to the local and regional economies, and foster local customs and culture. Festivals and events are critical components of a location's brand development. Festivals of food, religion, and spirituality during a particular season or harvesting a specific crop are the most popular social gatherings. They may include unique performances, rituals, and art exhibitions. As with businesses, places have diverse stakeholders with whom they must interact to build relationships and co-create value. As a result, local and national governments, citizens, corporate sector leaders, and marketers are required to develop, implement, and assess branding strategies that take economic, social, cultural, and technological resources into consideration. Nowadays, traditional communication and marketing strategies are no longer appropriate for place branding and raising awareness, and differentiating themselves in the digital era. Social media is a successful branding technique due to factors such as two-way communication, user-generated content, and information sharing between users and businesses and among users themselves. This study will examine well-known Asian social events that have contributed significantly to the development of regional destination brands while considering critical success elements. Due to the diversity of Asia and our wealth of information about it, there is numerous research on the Far East and South Asia. This paper will focus on the social events unfolding in Central Asia that are getting global attention due to the countries' increased openness to the rest of the world.

INTRODUCTION

A brand can be attributed to a promise, a perception, and whatever a customer sees, hears, reads, learns, and feels about a product, service, or company. Consumers also give the brand a special place in their brains, based on prior experiences, associations, and future expectations (Botti et al., 2018; Setianti et al., 2018; Uslay & Çiçek, 2018). Destination branding is a method used by a nation or territory to establish a strong position in the minds of its customers to become well-known across the world. The process of developing a destination brand includes employing icons, slogans, exhibits, and effective placement in various forms of promotional media (Uslay & Çiçek, 2018). Although a brand is not an outcome, it provides meaning and uniqueness in time and place. The attendance of cultural events has been increasing over time. However, the competition amongst such events and festivals have also increased (Palma et al., 2013; Pulido-Fernández & Sánchez-Rivero, 2010). The festival image is sometimes one of the critical elements of the region's brand-building process, and it is then ingrained in the finished tourism product. As a result, festival brands frequently impact the image of the entire area brand (Botti et al., 2018). Several multi-tiered factors play a role in the development of a destination brand, like structure or unstructured planning, culture, stakeholders, and communication strategies. This study discusses how social festivals play their role in developing destination brands in Asian countries.

Festivity is one of the core elements of the social spectrum of society. Festivals are gaining popularity for their ability to improve a region's image and attractiveness, improve recreational options, contribute to the local and regional economy, and boost local pride and culture. The festivals and events are indispensable for place branding (Rossolatos, 2018). Themes created by festivals play a significant role in developing destination brand image (Botti et al., 2018). There is a growing trend of developing event portfolios that comprise many interrelated events over time (Antchak et al., 2021). Such portfolios could be organic and do not require any institutionalization or publicity, and such events are deeply embedded within the community's traditions. The concept of Slowcity or Cittaslow (Bayraktar & Uslay, 2017) is safeguarding such approaches. The

Cittaslow movement's objectives are to avoid place standardization, preserve local values, improve quality of life, enable sustainable development, promote local economies, conserve nature, and assist cities in discovering their unique soul and character (Uslay & Çiçek, 2018). On the other hand, a structured portfolio is governed by a formal portfolio strategy and is distinguished by planned structures, strategic coordination, allocated investment, and periodic review (Ziakas & Getz, 2020). For the success of destination branding, an event should include events throughout the year neutralizing the seasonality effect, must have a broader breadth of activities and genres, should have a mix of both one-off and repeat events, and should cater to the need of both niche and mass markets, dispersed over a larger geographical area for continued customer engagement and should be able to generate media coverage for both local and international customers (Antchak et al., 2021).

Culture is most likely the most effective instrument for enhancing tourism and branding a location. It adds character to locations, creates distinct experiences for tourists, and is an unrivaled key to difference. Culture is perhaps the most potent weapon for branding and enhancing a place. Culture is a multifaceted entity comprised of social conventions and customs, language, dress, architecture, art, music, and gastronomy. Additionally, it is impacted by historical events and lifestyle, and surroundings, making imitation exceedingly difficult (Ozer, 2017). The social events are primarily associated with food, religion, and spiritual festivals celebrated at a specific time or the harvest of a particular product consisting of special performances, customs, and art displays (Maeng et al., 2016). There are several local festivals dedicated to honoring local culinary traditions. Build local product business and commerce, promote domestic and regional tourism, and generate sustainable destinations (Botti et al., 2018; Stevenson, 2016). Food is an integral part of foreign travel as an intangible legacy and cultural appeal (Amore & Roy, 2020). Food and cuisine have evolved into a critical component of a destination's image and a crucial draw element in visitors' decision-making processes (Naruetharadhol & Gebsoambut, 2020). Identifying and promoting regional meals and culinary

experiences may be an effective marketing approach for a particular place (Sengel et al., 2015). Numerous local destinations promote their cuisines by using regional dishes and produce and by organizing events and festivals (Amore & Roy, 2020; Schmudde, 2019). Another powerful branding approach for places is the organization of large-scale events (Uslay & Çiçek, 2018). Music festivals are also the primary source of the attractiveness of a local festival (Lee & Arcodia, 2011). Music-related events, such as festivals, offer venues for producing concurrent experiential events that deliver complete brand and inter-brand experiences. Festivals, in particular, play an essential role in the experience economy in addition to their distinctive multisensory orientation and interactive character (Rossolatos, 2018). There is a growing recognition of the fact that Music-centric communities may have enormous economic, employment, cultural, and social benefits to offer governments and other stakeholders (Bustomi & Avianto, 2021; Pulido-Fernández & Sánchez-Rivero, 2010).

Places, like brands, have a plethora of qualities and a diverse set of stakeholders that must work together to develop relationships and co-create value to succeed. As a result, local and national governments, residents, private sector authorities, and marketers must create, manage, and evaluate branding strategies that consider economic, social, cultural, and technical resources. The holding and organization of a festival involves many stakeholders that include the Government, local suppliers, local & foreign customers, the tourist sector, and others (Botti et al., 2018). The role of stakeholders in the success of events in the case of paying visitors, the Government, media, and agencies involved in artists' welfare is more vital than sponsors, local businesses, workers, and suppliers (Getz & Andersson, 2010). The role of the Government in promoting culture and place marketing is evident, and governments use different creative ways to embrace the art, culture, and topology to promote a destination (Setianti et al., 2018).

Due to their past historical background and geopolitical position, many countries have negative associations attached to them as the country brand. Traditionally, countries adopt an "advocacy approach" or broadcasting-based communication approach to rebrand themselves as destinations. A micro-

marketing strategy highlighting a country's relative advantages, as opposed to rational, "cold," and clinical advertising, is helpful since it avoids political and ideological confrontations. It is more important to be "relevant" to your target audience than to be "correct." Approaches like this one respect other people's political opinions but strive to restrict them by stressing the country's competitive advantages and possibilities. This strategy, which focuses on new features and services more suited to the target consumer, should have emotional and intellectual components (Aharoni & Grinstein, 2017). In the digital world, traditional communication and marketing strategies are insufficient for locations to generate awareness and differentiate themselves from competitors. Due to properties such as two-way communication, user-generated content, and information exchange between users and businesses, as well as among users themselves, social media is a potent branding tool (Uzunoglu, 2017). Nowadays, travelers conduct travel research on social media platforms such as TripAdvisor, Lonely Planet, Facebook, and content communities such as YouTube, Twitter, Instagram, forums, and blogs (Cox et al., 2009). Destination planners should collaborate to develop their social media strategy, as users are co-creators of location branding on social media. Users' participation is regarded to be more authentic, trustworthy, and reliable than that of authorities and partners (Uzunoglu, 2017).

Considering the key success factors, this paper will analyze the famous social events in Asia that are contributing a lot to developing regional destination brands. As Asia is diverse and we have there are many studies available about the Far East and South Asia. This study will focus on social events in Central Asia that are gaining world attention after the opening up of the countries.

Social Events in Asia

This part describes festivals based on the location principle. In case festivals have a similar idea, but different geographic locations, the differences in celebrations will be highlighted.

Uzbekistan**Navruz festival**

The word Navruz itself means a "new day" if translated from Persian "نوروز." The spelling and pronunciation of the word Navruz (Novruz, Navruz, Nooruz, Nevruz, Nauruz) may vary from country to country. More than 300 million people worldwide celebrate this special day yearly on March 21 for over 3000 years in the Middle East, the Caucasus, the Central Asia region, the Black Sea basin, and even the Balkans. The date of the celebration refers to the astronomical vernal equinox, when daytime and nighttime are equal to 12 hours each. Moreover, this magical date means the 180-degree shift in seasons in the northern and southern hemispheres of the Earth, Spring comes to the north, and the south faces autumn. In 2009, the United Nations (UN) inscribed this celebration on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity due to its wide celebration by various cultures and countries (UN, 2021).

Throughout the centuries, the arrival of spring has been considered one of the most joyful events in people's lives. Since the warm season arrives in the country, nature awakens and its decorations are changing. In Uzbekistan, people prepare very carefully for this holiday and celebrate for 15-20 days. Since the beginning of March, people anticipate Navruz, "hashars" (translated from Persian/Arabian as "joint labor, charity") are organized in the "mahallas" (quarters of every city) across the country - people clean irrigation ditches, whiten the bottom parts of trees, and dig gardens.

A few words should be addressed to Hashar itself. In Muslim countries, Hashar means the day of voluntary gratuitous work, and it is one of the ancient traditions of the Uzbek people. Its essence is a combination of prosperity, kindness, and solidarity. The inherent collectivism is a part of the Uzbek national character. Therefore, the tradition of public Hashar is not only to jointly carry out public work under the guidance of order but also to combine the reverence of folk traditions and maintain them from century to century. Everyone starts Hashar by cleaning their own house and the yard, a part of the street nearby, and then in the neighborhoods, labor communities, parks, and throughout the country. Each young man knows the meaning of the annual cleaning of our city for the community. Wise Aksakals (the oldest people in the

neighborhood) keep in mind the traditions of our people and teach their grandchildren how to plant trees and take care of the gardens (OrexCA, 2022). The culture of Hashar directly correlates to the Navruz celebration since it supports the values of solidarity and peace within families and between generations. Thus, it contributes to friendship among people and cultural diversity (UN, 2021).

The traditions of celebrating Navruz are the same throughout the region and have remained unchanged for centuries. However, in the last ten years, Navruz Day in the Central Asian republics has become an officially recognized and celebrated public holiday. At the same time, such modern attributes of celebrating Navruz like concerts in parks and squares, trade fairs, and national equestrian competitions (OrexCA, 2022). Unlike the traditional European New Year, being a local "New Year", Navruz is celebrated in the afternoon, but always starts with greeting family members. In the next thirteen days, Uzbeks visit relatives, purchase and plant fruit trees, and gather in cheerful companies in the bosom of spring nature. Different people celebrate it in different ways. However, the main idea of the celebration is the rebirth of nature, the triumph of life, and hopes for a generous harvest year.

Every mahalla has its teahouse, and according to tradition, each mahalla starts celebrating Navruz in its teahouse. In the teahouse, delicious foods are prepared in huge cauldrons. Residents of the mahalla, as well as residents of neighboring mahallas, are invited to the holiday. There are a few foods that are cooked for the Navruz day only. Among them are sumalak, halim (khalisa), and a special tugrama pilaf. Being a holy and sacred meal, Sumalak is cooked with the use of wheat turned into porridge by old women of the mahalla for more than 24 hours, where young girls could drop small stones into the pot and make a wish. According to tradition, in case a girl finds a stone in her piala (Uzbek cups), her wish will come true in the future. Such a joint cooking activity lets the elder generations pass the recipe of this ancient food to their successors and share the wisdom. The recipe of sumalak may vary from region to region, but the idea remains the same since Zoroastrianism times.

Uzbeks believe that the more cheerful and joyful the Navruz celebration is, the more generous their nature will be towards people. Therefore, the ritual songs of

Navruz are played the whole day, while people are dancing and enjoying the arrival of spring, giving each other small gifts, as well as helping orphans and the poor by making donations. Giving out sumalak and pilaf is a tradition that is nurtured by the people of Uzbekistan (CALEND, 2022b). Foreigners are welcomed to participate in the event. Many foreign embassies in Uzbekistan congratulate their local staff members with Navruz and join various culture and food fairs across the country to share the moment.

Boysun Bahori festival

The Boysun Bahori Festival is a celebration of unique cultures! Nowadays, unique rituals and traditions are being lost in general. However, in remote from large cities, you can still see a “special” local culture. The purpose of this festival is to collect and demonstrate the heritage of the past, which is carefully preserved not only in Boysun but also in other regions of Uzbekistan. In 2002, a year after the UN inscribed this celebration on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity, the first folklore festival "Boysun Bahori" took place in Uzbekistan in the idyllic Village Padang (Boysun Region). The Boysun region is very beautiful in springtime, when the surrounding mountains are full of green trees and grass as well as flowering meadows - that is why this event is held at this time of the year and therefore it is called "Boysun bahori" which means Boysun spring (UZ Daily, 2019). Being a center of a district in Surkhandarya province, Baisun is a cosy town near the Ketmen-Chapty Mountains in the Baisuntau Range and is located 150 km north of Termez city in the southern part of Uzbekistan. The legends of the Baysun region revolve around the national hero Alpomysh (originating from the pre-Islamic pagan culture), who has been famous for the past thousand years for his courage (Turkestan Travel, 2021). People pass this legend as well as rituals across generations. Every end of April during the Boysun Bakhori International Folk Festival in the foothills of the Baysun region, Uzbek build a large camp with yurts and handicraft stalls, where all foreign local guests of the festival have the opportunity to get familiarized not only with folklore traditions and performances, but also with handicraft creations of Uzbek architects, with bright national costumes, and of course, with delicious Uzbek cuisine. On the

established stage in the open sky camp, the national melodies are performed for the guests of the event by folklore bands and solo performers from all over the country. Guests are offered Uzbek traditional games and amusements including buzkashi, kurash belt wrestling, horse races, cocks fighting, and many more.

The international music festival “Shark Taronalari”

Shark Taronalari is an International Music Festival held in Samarkand city in August once every 2 years since 1997. In 2019, during the XII International Music Festival "Sharq Taronalari", the performances of singers from over 32 countries were evaluated in two categories: folk music or professional song, and contemporary music or traditional song (SPUTNIK, 2019, 2021). Music plays an important role during the various phases of business cycles in real life (de Lucio & Palomeque, 2022).

Many events held during the festival include open-air concerts, creative meetings, special programs in the form of scientific and press conferences, various round tables, presentations, and master classes for guests. Moreover, various exhibitions of national instruments and crafts are organized (EXPLORER, 2022). The music festival ends with a solemn awarding ceremony for the winners and prize-runners of the competition as well as a great gala concert in the Samarkand Registan Square. The winner of the Grand Prix of the festival is awarded \$ 10,000. The 1st place winner receives \$ 5,000 while prize-runners receive \$ 3,500 and \$ 2,500 respectively. Uzbekistan invites foreign and local musicians, famous artists, composers, and representatives of international art festivals to participate as the independent and international jury. The competition is broadcasted live by the local TV and radio company on large monitors across the streets of Samarkand. Moreover, the International Music Festival "Sharq Taronalari" is broadcasted by 41 media companies from over 20 countries.

The “Asrlar Sadosi” festival

The festival of traditional culture "Asrlar sadosi" (The Echo of the Ages) is annually held in various historical and cultural centers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and presents a great variety of folk traditions and customs, applied art, national cuisine, and unique intangible heritage of the region where the festival is

held. In the Kashkadarya region, it is the competition of horsemen "ulok-kupkari" and the art of "storytellers-bakhshi"; in Khiva city, these are ram fights and carpet weaving; in ancient Bukhara city, guests are invited to evaluate the craft of golden sew art and the exclusive local art of gold minting. The festival held in the Tashkent region demonstrates the exciting performances of rope-walkers (IA-CENTR, 2011).

For the very first time, the festival was held in 2008 in the Kitab district of the Kashkadarya region. At the festival, products of masters of applied art, delights of national cuisine, unique traditions of folk games, the art of masters of street shows, performances of folklore groups, and a festival of national dress art were presented. In recent years, the "Asrlar Sadosi" was held in the Akkurgan and Bostanlyk districts of the Tashkent region in 2009, near the historical monument of Ichan-Kala in Khiva in 2010, and in the city of Bukhara in 2011. From time to time, foreign guests and creators are presenting their art in "Asrlar Sadosi". In 2011, Japanese calligrapher Koichi Honda (worldwide known as one of the finest Arab calligraphers living today) participated in Bukhara's event. Nowadays, some of his works have been included in the permanent exhibition of the British Museum in London. This unique experience makes the guests of the festival from around the world willing to come over again (GAZETA, 2012).

The "Stihia" music festival near the Aral Sea

The widely known in Central Asia "Stihia" festival has been held since 2017, I have conducted it yearly in Muynak city in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (part of Uzbekistan) in the north of Uzbekistan (stihia.org, n.d.). The city is surrounded by the sands of the dried Aral Sea. In the USSR times, Muynak was a port where ships carrying cotton and fish were docked. However, today, a small ship graveyard is the only remaining from those times. For two days, rave culture lovers dance and relax while listening to DJs and music from performers from Russia, Turkey, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, and Uzbekistan. In addition to the entertainment part, the festival is positioned as an environmental action: volunteers who arrive in Muynak plant trees. In 2021, more than five thousand shrubs and fruit trees were planted in two days to stop the expansion of the pesticide-poisoned Aralkum desert and help the local ecosystem. Various art

installations in the form of ships and fish help to carry the unforgettable atmosphere of the festival (Obglodin et al., 2021). This project was created with the support of the Ministry of Tourism and Sports of Uzbekistan, the Russian corporation "Rosatom", the State Committee for Ecology and Environmental Protection, the State Forestry Committee, and the Council of Ministers of Karakalpakstan. Further, the organizers of the festival introduced the "Stihia N+1" environmental science forum for scientists, researchers, business leaders, and artists to explore how human activity impacts nature. Photographers over the world attend the "Stihia" rave at the bottom of the Aral Sea (the fourth largest inland water body on the planet in the past) to shoot the unique scenes of the Dead Sea and attract the attention of the world to this ecological disaster.

The National Souvenirs festival

On October 28, 2021, by the initiative of the Cultural Heritage Agency under the Ministry of Tourism and Sports, a festival of national souvenirs was organized for the first time in all regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The festival aims to accelerate the development of domestic and foreign tourism, widely promote the cultural and historical heritage of the country among the citizens and foreign tourists, to strengthen the image of Uzbekistan as a safe place for traveling and recreation (UZ Daily, 2021b).

The attraction of visitors to museums and cultural heritage sites of the republic through the establishment of trade in national souvenirs created by the festival participants will contribute to the sustainable socio-economic development of the regions, ensuring the employment of artisans and their material and moral support. The official opening ceremony of the festival was held at the State Museum of the History of Applied Arts and Crafts of Uzbekistan.

The "Silk and Spices" festival in Bukhara

The "Silk and Spices" festival is an annual event held for several days at the end of May in Bukhara, a city on the Great Silk Road. Thousands of years ago, caravans loaded with silk and spices were moving from China to Europe, passing through a mountain and lifeless deserts, stopping in oases. Bukhara was one of those cities lying on a trade route from East to West.

The grand masters of pottery, minting, carpet weaving, gold embroidery, and other crafts lived in this ancient city. "Silk and Spices" is designed to revive the cultural heritage of the Great Silk Road and demonstrate the richness of the traditions of local craftsmen (UZ Daily, 2021a). Tourists from all over the world visit this festival yearly. Uzbeks dress up in national costumes, while performers, dancers, and acrobats all together entertain the guests. Starting with the medieval warriors lining up near the walls of the Ark fortress, and caravans of camels and horses passing along the street connecting the trading domes of Bukhara, creating the impression of a journey a thousand years ago (FERGANA, 2019). After the opening ceremony, guests enjoy a unique trade fair, where the works of various folk craftsmen and artisans are widely presented - gold embroidery national clothes of craftswomen from Samarkand, Kashkadarya, and Surkhandarya, samples of metal chased plates from Bukhara, and porcelain from the Fergana Valley. Moreover, tourists can purchase widely known fabrics such as khan atlas and adras. In the end of the "Silk and Spices" festival, a traditional concert is organized in the Poi-Kalyan architectural complex, where visitors can listen to Uzbek folk music.

Tajikistan

The 'Roof of the World' Festival

The 'Roof of the World' festival is the annual music event conducted in Khorog city in Tajikistan since 2008. It usually takes place in Central City Park, "Chorbog". Khorog is 12 hours away by car from Dushanbethe capital of Tajikistan. The event's program includes a wide cross-section of folklore groups from the Pamirs and other regions of Tajikistan, as well as performances by foreign ensembles from neighboring Afghanistan, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan. However, organizers invite music bands from all over the world. In 2019, participants from Poland taught guests how to play their national musical instruments (TRAVEL CALENDAR, 2021b).

The idea of the festival is to preserve and promote traditional and modern music genres and dance of the peoples of the Pamirs and other regions of Tajikistan (Firouz, 2020). In addition to traditional music, dance, and theatrical performances, guests can get

acquainted with the exotic national cuisine of the Pamirs, purchase authentic musical instruments and examples of applied arts, attend craft masterclasses, and see thematic documentaries from the participating countries (VECHERKA, 2019). Usually, the festival takes place in the summer period. However, in 2020, the organizers conducted the 13th annual festival "Roof of the World" online from September 14 to October 4 due to the COVID-19 pandemic (SPUTNIK, 2019). In addition to regular participants, ensembles from the U.S.A., India, and Latvia presented their performances.

Kyrgyzstan

World Nomad Games

During the 2nd summit of the Turkic Council in Bishkek in 2012, Kyrgyzstan proposed organizing the World Nomad Games to revive, develop, and protect the national games of the Turkic people. Since September 2014, this event has taken place in Kyrgyzstan once every two years (Alymbekov, 2018). The Games include "pull the rope" and archery as well as horse racing and competitions, such as "er enish" (Kyrgyz horseback wrestling) and "kok-boru". Kok-boru (translated to English as "Grey Wolf") is a game where players throw the dead goat or sheep at each other while riding a horse. The tradition came from the past when men were going out to hunt the wolf packs, catching them on the go and throwing them over each other playfully (WNG, 2018). Besides horseback competitions, guests can watch the competition in different types of national wrestling such as Kurash, Alysh, and Goresh. Moreover, World Nomad Games include Intellectual games competitions such as Toguz Korgool (similar to the Chinese game "Go"), Mangala, and Oware.

World Nomad Games became a bridge connecting people of different nationalities and confessions. Despite the era of digitalization, they could save the heritage of Turkic-speaking countries and peoples. Today, the festival's concept invites countries to participate and introduce their cultures and performances. For these purposes, several zones such as "ethno-dance", "ethno-fashion", "ethno-bazaar", and "Narrative art" were organized. In 2018, more than 350 actors, singers, and musicians from Germany, Great Britain, Japan, Kazakhstan, the United Arab Emirates, Romania, and Scotland, as well as the

entities of the Russian Federation, arrived at the ethnocultural festival. Competitions were held in one of the most beautiful places of Kyrgyzstan - on the coast of the blue Issyk-Kul Lake and in the Kyrchyn gorge. According to the rating of international experts, the third World Nomad Games were included in the three most important events of 2018 (WNG, 2018). The 4th competition to be organized in Turkey has been postponed to September 2022 due to the epidemiological situation in the world (Daily SABAH, 2022).

Kok Boru (Buzkashi) competition as a part of Nowruz celebrations

The event takes place in spring (as well as in other Central Asian countries) and is centered on Kok-Boru's national pastime, nomadic sport. Nowruz celebrations in Kyrgyzstan Celebration start with preparing national food, followed by Kok-boru competitions the next day. After the matches, people return to the Nowruz celebration (Antonov, 2021).

Turkmenistan

Turkmen Horse Festival

This national holiday of Turkmenistan is celebrated with horse races, equestrian games, a fair, concerts, and dances, as well as a beauty contest for the Akhal-Teke horses. Established in 1992, the festival takes place every last Sunday of April in all regions of Turkmenistan (bigasia.ru, 2019). Akhal-Teke horses are one of the oldest cultivated horse breeds in the world. The name of the breed is composed of two words: the name of the Akhal oasis and the Turkmen tribe "Teke". The horses are widely distinguished not only by their speed and beauty but also by their endurance since they can win at long-race distances (Vladimir, 2021).

The celebration starts with horse racing in the Ashgabat region. Twenty participants should complete a 60 km marathon. Moreover, unlike in other similar competitions, the winner is not the one who is the first one to cross the finish line. Instead, the highest importance is given to the ability to bring the horse to the end of the distance in good condition and not being injured. Moreover, the horse's pulse should not exceed 64 bpm. Besides horse racing, guests can visit exhibitions and fairs as well as

international scientific conferences dedicated to horse breeding (CALEND, 2022a).

Melon Day

The Melon Day festival (est. 1994) takes place every second Sunday of August, since this is the month when melons are harvested in Turkmenistan. On the day of the festival, all guests have an opportunity to taste the most diverse varieties of local melons (RFERL, 2013). Turkmen melons remain a favorite fruit of the people from the ex-USSR. Turkmenistan considers melons as a part of its great heritage, national wealth, and a symbol of the talent and hard work of local farmers who continue the traditions of their ancestors. Moreover, concerts and fairs are organized in different cities of the country. At the end of the festival, the President of Turkmenistan awards the best melon growers of the country in the "Golden melon of the Golden Age" competition (CALEND, 2022a).

Kazakhstan

Nauryz

Similar to Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan celebrates the Nauryz yearly in March. Additionally, to the Uzbek approach to celebration, Kazakhs have a tradition to burn archa twigs and fumigate their houses to get rid of negative spirits and clean their souls. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, Kazakhstan held the II International online festival of choreographic creativity "Nauryz invites friends" in Kostanay in 2021. Participants from all post-USSR countries were invited to demonstrate their dancing skills in the broadcast online competition. At the end of the fest, all participants performed the joint Kazakh folk dance "Kara zhorga" (DCKR, 2021).

The AlmaFest: Tekeli Apple Festival

According to historical recordings, Kazakhstan is considered the motherland of ancient apples. The Traditional Tekele Apple Festival is a great entertainment event conducted every year (KHABAR, 2019). It is dedicated to the celebration of the Day of the City of Almaty since Almaty city means the "father of apples" in the Kazakh language (Bulatkulova, 2021). The festival area is traditionally divided into several activity zones, such as an open-air contemporary art platform "Alma Art", "Alma Drive" playground for

sports activities, and an exhibition fair "Alma Master" where works of local craftsmen are demonstrated. AlmaFest demonstrates their music skills at the "Alma Auen" music zone. Moreover, children are offered various masterclasses and workshops at the "Alma Otbasay" zone. Finally, since the symbol of the festival is the apple, guests are offered to taste and purchase various foods such as pastries, preserves, apple jams, and apples themselves in a dedicated "Alma Bazar" zone (ALMATY, 2021).

"Four E" festival

The "Four E" is the largest ethnic festival in Kazakhstan that gathers people of different cultures and nationalities under the same Roof. The festival's name stands for "4-E" - Ecology, Ethnicity, Emotions, and Evolution (TRAVEL CALENDAR, 2021a). The organizers of the event believe that these four areas can set the right vector of development for any person. The first "Four E" festival was held in 2010, and it has been run for over ten years in various natural zones of the Almaty region. The idea of the festival is to promote creativity, sport, self-development, and mind ecology. The story began with five friends willing to go out to nature for holidays. They invited their friends and people who are sticking to a healthy lifestyle, are fond of music, creativity, and are engaged in self-development. They were surprised to see 1,500+ people arrive. Traditionally, the "Four E" is conducted closer to the end of summer. In 2021, the festival took place between 18 and 27 August (ATMASFERA, 2021). Since its start, the 4-E has developed its traditions. This includes tasting watermelons as a welcome food upon the entrance of the festival city, playing 'ring-around-the-rosy' as well as decorating tents and territory with bright fabrics of four colors symbolizing 4-Es: green for ecology, purple for evolution, pink for emotions, and orange for ethnicity.

The fest has several zones dedicated to different activities. In some, participants have yoga classes. In others, they are offered dancing and sports activities. The festival is equally suitable for adults and children. Being under constant mentorship, kids are offered various masterclasses and interactive games, while adult participants can enjoy going to rope zones, archery areas, and other activities. The nature of the festival allows participants to have activities non-stop

for 24 hours. The "over the night" program includes sitting around a large joint fireplace and enjoying the chillout music. Such activities include playing ethnic musical instruments. Singers and bands from Kazakhstan, Russia, Armenia, Ukraine, India, and other countries participate in FourE. Visitors can get to the festival town by car or by bus from Almaty (TRAVEL CALENDAR, 2021a).

Jezkiik ethno-music festival

Jezkiik music festival is a yearly event in June or August in the Ulytau region of Kazakhstan. According to the legend, the Kazakh poet Kakimbek Salikov met Jezkiik - the patron of saigas in Kazakhstan (KARAGANDA, 2018). Being amazed by her extreme beauty, he wrote a poem that has been further transformed into a song. Originating in the ancient steppes of the Kazakh land, the song became the anthem of the festival "Jezkiik", and according to the beliefs of Kazakhs, this song has value for all nations of the world. Being an Ethno music event, the festival invites participants from various countries. In 2019, alongside local singers, musical bands from Hungary, Spain, Italy, and Serbia demonstrated their traditional music (KARANGANDA, 2019).

Despite being a music festival, Jezkiik includes the exhibition of works by masters of applied art "Uly Dala zhagyrygy", where guests can find crafted items made of leather, felt, and wood. In the food zone, guests are invited to observe the master classes on national Kazakh cuisine cooking foods (KAZINFORM, 2019). Everyone can learn how to cook the traditional food of nomads, taste delicious masterpieces of the best chefs in the region and learn more about the gastronomic culture of the steppe peoples.

Pakistan

Basant Kite Flying Festival

Appearing in the mid-16th century in the Mughal Empire, the Basant Mela is widely celebrated in India, Pakistan, and several other countries of South Asia. In Pakistan, Lahore (Punjab state) is the center of the celebration. Translated from Hindi, "Basant" means "yellow" and "Mela" means "the assembly". By the beginning of the Basant Mela celebration in mid-February, the peasant fields look like an endless yellow carpet stretching far beyond the horizon because of mustard blossoms. Yellow color predominates not

only in rural areas but also in cities since people wear yellow clothes, prepare festive food, decorate streets and houses, using many shades of yellow to welcome Spring. Being a part of Basant Mela celebrations, the Basant Kite Flying Festival is a unique event in the world and takes place on 26-27 January yearly. People fly their kites from the rooftops and participate in the competition where they should bring down the opponent's kite. Due to many accidents and injuries, the use of kites during the event in Lahore, Kasur, and Rawalpindi was prohibited by the Government of Pakistan since 2009 (Khalid, 2018). Guests of the festival are offered a variety of activities, including horse and folk dancing, puppet shows, arts, and handicrafts, as well as tasting Kebab and sumptuous Punjabi food (CEP, 2021a).

Mela Chiraghan (festival of lights)

Mela Chiraghan is held in Pakistan annually in Lahore, not far from the ancient Shalimar Garden. The duration of the event is 3 days, and the last day is for women only. This holiday is dedicated to Urs, the anniversary of the death of the Sufi poet and Saint Shah Hussein, who lived in the 16th century. Mela Chiraghan is one of the main festivals in Lahore (Emekli, 2021). Traditionally, devotees from all over the country come to Shah Hussein's shrine to lay floral wreaths at his grave and light up candles as well as fulfill their prayers and desires (Qureshi, 2019). The distinguishing characteristic of this festival is the distribution of langar (free food) to poor people and those in need. After throwing oil wax and candles into the "Alao" bonfire at the shrine of Hussain, people lit up cotton lamps hoping that they would fulfill their desires. The fire remains for the entire duration of the Urs (Hasan, 2016). In 2022, the festival will start on 26 March.

Shandur Polo Festival

Shandur Polo Festival is a three-day event that takes place on 7th-9th July in the mountains on the Shandur pass at 3700 meters altitude. This makes it the highest polo ground in the world. Thousands of people arrive and live in a tent cities due to the absence of guest houses. Participation in the festival is considered a privilege, and local celebrities take part in it every year (KHILARI, 2021). The competition between the best teams from Gilgit and Chitral is an essential part of

the festival. The tournament is organized and financed by the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Culture and Tourism Authority. During the days of the competition, guests can attend zones of national Pakistani music and dance. Active leisure time lovers are offered trout fishing and mountaineering, trekking and hiking as well as horse riding activities.

Lok Virsa Folk Festival

Lok Virsa is the National Cultural Center and Museum of Pakistan (LOKVIRSA, 2021). This fascinating place provides guests and tourists with a complete understanding of the Pakistani national handicrafts. A 7-day annual event takes place in Islamabad in early November, featuring folk dances and music, folkloric performances, food courts, exotic craft markets, and other activities. All provinces of the country have their own tastefully decorated pavilions where they present their culture and cuisine (Tribune, 2020). Gilgit-Baltistan, Azad Jammu, and Kashmir provinces held cultural nights with live concerts of folk artists and performers. Traditionally, "chadarposhi" and "dastarbandi" ceremonies open the festival, while at the end of the festival, the most talented artisans and performers are awarded prizes and certificates during the special colorful ceremony (The News, 2021).

Sibi Mela (Baluchistan)

Sibi Mela is an annual event that usually takes place at the end of February. According to historical recordings, tribes of Baluchistan met in Sibi (a small historical town in Baluchistan) to trade livestock (CEP, 2021b). The festival features tent pegging, cultural performances, animal bazaars, camel races as well as exhibitions of arts and handicrafts. Each tribe represents its tribal dresses and folk dances. Nowadays, the festival is not only a place where tribal people meet to discuss the cattle, horse, and camel breeding development, but it is also a part of the cultural heritage of the country (HINDUKUSH, 2022).

Kalash Festival

Kalash valley is a picturesque place in the Chitral region of the northern part of Pakistan. The Ministry of Religious Affairs and Inter-faith Harmony of Pakistan supports celebrations of various important religious festivals of Pakistani minorities. Having

slightly different traditions, religions (pagan), customs, and languages, Kalashi people try to maintain their cultural heritage. Kalash festivals are associated with local religious celebrations at different times of the year. Whole villages come together and participate in dancing and singing performances. They have two main annual festivals that attract local and international visitors: Chilam Joshi and Uchal. Chilam Joshi is a spring festival celebrated annually at the end of May. The first day of the event is "Milk Day". On this day, Kalashes trade or exchange dairy products with the use of milk accumulated ten days before the event. The idea of the festival is to celebrate the beginning of the summer season. Single people seek a spouse to marry. Participants are sending a peace message to the world community (Pakistan Explorer, 2021). Uchal takes place in the middle of July when people celebrate harvest for two days by dancing in circles, singing, and feasting (Tour Rangers, 2021).

Conclusion

Annual festivals and events taking place in Central Asian countries are demonstrating the variety of cultures, customs, and traditions of local nationalities and minorities. The importance of such festivals is maintaining cultural heritage for the next generations, creating partnerships between countries, and providing a unique experience to foreign tourists and participants. Guests not only observe the celebrations but are very welcome to participate in various activities and performances, networking with locals and internationals.

As mentioned above, some festivals have a common ground in different countries. However, supporting the idea of (Ozer, 2017), having differences in celebrations, the events do not fall into imitating each other. Navruz is celebrated in all Central Asian (CA) countries. Meanwhile, approaches and traditions might be different as in the case of Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. Both the Melon festival in Turkmenistan and AlmaFest in Kazakhstan have the same idea, but the symbols of these festivals and the scale of the events are different. Some festivals are being run in different locations, making each year unlike the previous one (Asrlar Sadosi festival).

Besides preserving traditions, the festivals have commercial grounds. Asrlar Sadosi festival gives an

economic boost to the regions where it is being organized. The widespread broadcasting of festivals via mass-media helps to promote local countries' brands on the international market and stimulate tourism and the economy. "Silk and Spices", "World Nomad Games", "Basant Kite", "Jezkiik", "Roof of the World", and other festivals attract tourists all over the world. Kalash valley has approximately 40 hotels that are very dependent on tourists (thefrontierpost.com, n.d.). Therefore, those festivals have been receiving high attention and support from local governmental authorities (Botti et al., 2018). The recent disruption led by the COVID-19 pandemic forced some of the above festivals, such as "Roof of the World" in Tajikistan and "Nauryz invites friends" in Kazakhstan, to be run online. Others have been postponed for the next year (World Nomad Games). The online festivals may not bring sufficient finance to the organizers but might allow them to maintain the interest of foreigners and could be used as a good promotion now, aiming to attract visitors once the traveling bans are down.

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